

MRI vs. US 3D computational models of carotid arteries: a Fluid Structure Interaction case-study

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Abstract The development and progression of atherosclerotic carotid plaque causes an ongoing stenosis in the arterial lumen. This process might lead to the disastrous thin fibrous cap rupture ending to thromboembolism and stroke. Carotid artery disease is the primary cause for ischemic stroke in the EU, thus escalating the necessity of the development of specialized software for risk stratification and patient management in carotid artery disease. In this study, we present a comparison between ultrasound-based and MRI-based 3D carotid artery models to examine if US-based models can be used to evaluate the hemodynamic status of the carotid vasculature compared with the respective MRI-based models which are considered as the most accurate depiction of the carotid vasculature. Two-way fluid structure interaction blood flow simulations were carried out on the full 3D models (i.e., lumen, outer wall and plaque components). Our work revealed a promising similitude between the two methods of reconstruction in terms of geometrical as well as simulated hemodynamic parameters which are vital for the hemodynamic status of the cerebral vasculature, therefore establishing carotid US as a possible MRI substitute for an initial carotid artery disease evaluation.

Keywords computational models; carotid; ultrasound; MRI; blood flow simulations.

1 Introduction

Stroke constitutes one of the most well-known causes of death in the EU resulting to annual toll of 440,000 deaths. Besides death, stroke is mainly responsible for significant disabilities in adults with more than one out of two stroke survivors resulting in being completely dependent on the 24 hour care of other people for simple activities. The total annual costs linked to stroke reach the amount of almost €45 billion, including both direct and indirect costs for productivity loss and health care [1, 2].

The progression of carotid artery disease which results in enlarged atheromatic plaques which can be prone to erosion or rupture is considered as one of the most critical causes of stroke. The rupture of the atheromatic plaques results to thromboembolism and subsequently, cerebral infarction. Stenoses larger than 50% from asymptomatic plaques within the internal carotid artery (ICA) result to thromboembolisms that add up to more than 10% of all strokes. This intensifies the need of novel risk stratification tools which will improve patient management in cases of moderate to severe carotid artery disease.

In this context, many studies on modelling the biological processes that are connected to atherosclerosis and simulating the progression of atheromatic plaques have been published in the literature [3-7]. Most of these studies are based on idealized 2D models representing the carotid vasculature and only a small number of studies have used patient-specific 3D arterial models. Patient-specific 3D arterial models can be created utilizing several carotid imaging modalities, and, either Computed Tomography (CT) images, Magnetic Resonance Angiography (MRA) images or UltraSound (US) images, respectively. The 3D models (lumen, outer wall and plaque components) are then used to calculate important hemodynamic factors such as Endothelial Shear Stresses (ESS), Plaque Structural Stress (PSS) and identify areas of low ESS, which, in turn, are used to simulate the infiltration of lipoproteins and inflammatory cells within the layers of the arterial wall.

In this work, we present a proof-of-concept study which provides a comparison between MRI-based and US-based 3D carotid arterial models representing the lumen, the arterial wall and the carotid plaque for one patient with a mild carotid stenosis. The 3D reconstruction of the models was performed using in-house developed algorithms and results on peak time-averaged ESS (TAESS), areas of low ESS, qualitative assessment of the areas of peak ESS and geometrical measurements are presented.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Cardiovascular MR and US image acquisition protocols

One patient with >50% carotid stenosis (i.e., following the NASCET stenosis assessment criterion) using a 1.5-T whole-body system (Signa HDx, GE Healthcare, Waukesha, WI, USA) with a bilateral four-channel phased-array carotid coil (Machnet BV, Eelde, the Netherlands) from the TAXINOMISIS cohort was used in this study. The subject provided written informed consent and enrolled in the TAXINOMISIS clinical study (www.clinicaltrials.gov; ID: NCT03495830) protocol which was approved by the local competent ethics committee. The acquisition settings for the MRI sequences were the following: (i) TOF images: repetition time: 23 ms, effective echo time: 3.2 ms, field of view [FOV]: 160 mm, section thickness: 1 mm; (ii) fast-spin echo double-inversion recovery prepared sequences (T1W): repetition time: 1428.57 ms, effective echo time: 7.672 ms, FOV: 100 mm, section thickness: 3 mm; (iii) (T2W): repetition time: 1379.31 ms, effective echo time: 99.74 ms, FOV: 100 mm, section thickness: ≤ 2.5 mm (iv) (PDW): repetition time: 1379.31 ms, effective echo time: 7.67 ms, FOV: 100 mm, section thickness: ≤ 2.5 mm. The acquired data were stored in DICOM format. The US transversal and longitudinal images from the carotid bifurcations of interest were acquired from a GE Healthcare LOGIQE9 scanner.

2.1.1 3D reconstruction of the carotid artery using US

The methodology that was used to perform the 3D reconstruction of the patient-specific carotid artery from US images is already presented in the literature [8, 9]. The process is divided in two steps. The first step mainly involves deep learning techniques with convolutional neural networks, to perform the segmentation of the US images and the automated extraction of the lumen and wall segments, from both longitudinal and transversal images. The second step, involves the automated 3D reconstruction using the segmented lumen and wall contours. The longitudinal contours are used to extract the centerline of the vessel as well as information about diameters along the centerline, while transversal contours are used to define the shapes of the cross-sections along the centerline. All the aforementioned data are represented as a set of B-spline curves and NURBS surfaces, that are subsequently used in the meshing process to obtain the final geometry of the patient-specific carotid artery.

2.1.2 3D reconstruction of the carotid artery and plaque tissue components using MRI

The 3D carotid arterial model reconstruction pipeline relies on a sequence of magnetic resonance images (MRI), including ToF, T1w, T2w and PD series. Briefly, the TOF sequence is used for the reconstruction of the lumen, while the fusion of T1w, T2w and PD series are used for the reconstruction of the arterial wall, as well as the plaque components. The three models are aligned and co-registered in a later phase for the creation of the final arterial model. The reconstruction process is based on a novel methodology which consists of the following three steps:

1. **Segmentation of the region of interest.** To segment the regions of interest (lumen, outer wall and plaque components), three deep learning models have been created. More specifically, two experts have annotated 485 tuples of ToF, T1w, T2w and PD images from 42 different patients. This process resulted in a training dataset which was used to train three UNET models for the aforementioned region of interest.

2. **3D level set.** A morphological operator is applied to the 3D volume of the stacked 2D segmented frames in order to produce the 3D surface model.

3. **3D meshing.** Marching cubes algorithm is applied to the 3D surface model, resulting to the final reconstructed arterial model. Figure 1 depicts the six 3D reconstructed models that were used in the study.

Fig. 1 MRI-based 3D model depicted on the left (lumen in yellow, plaque in pink and wall in transparency) and US-based model (lumen in pink, plaque in green and wall in transparency) depicted on the right, respectively

2.2 Blood Flow simulations

Blood flow simulations were carried out for all six models (three MRI-based and 3 US-based). The same boundary conditions were used for every couple of arterial models. Patient-specific boundary conditions were used for each couple. At the inlet, the patient specific mean arterial pressure (MAP) was used, deriving from the systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) measurements that were recorded. MAP was calculated as [10]:

$$MAP = \frac{SBP + 2(DBP)}{3}. \quad (1)$$

Regarding the outlets (i.e., ICA and ECA), patient-specific mass flow rates were used as outlet boundary conditions. The mass flow rate profiles were calculated from the patient- and artery-specific flow velocity measurements which were acquired from the respective US images. In order to avoid inaccuracies at the mass flow rate calculations, the 3D models were trimmed in order to avoid any side branches after the bifurcation site, a fact that would affect the flow distribution within the artery of interest.

In order to model blood flow in our simulations, we used the Navier-Stokes and the continuity equations:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho(\mathbf{v} \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \nabla \bullet \boldsymbol{\tau} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \bullet (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the blood velocity vector and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor, which is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = -p\boldsymbol{\delta}_{ij} + 2\mu\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}, \quad (4)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, μ is the blood dynamic viscosity, p is the blood pressure and ε_{ij} is the strain tensor calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{v} + \nabla \mathbf{v}^T). \quad (5)$$

A two-way FSI approach regarding the deformable wall blood flow simulations was used in this section. In FSI simulations, the blood domain is deformable since we take into account the deformation of the arterial wall. Therefore, the equation of momentum conservation is used:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho((\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{w}) \bullet \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \nabla \bullet \boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{f}^B, \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the blood density, \mathbf{v} is the blood velocity vector, \mathbf{w} is the moving mesh velocity vector, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor and \mathbf{f}^B are the total body forces.

In our simulations, blood was treated as Newtonian fluid with a density $\rho=1050$ kg/m³ and dynamic viscosity $\mu=0.0035$ Pa s.

Regarding the arterial wall domain, the following momentum conservation equation is used:

$$\nabla \boldsymbol{\tau}_s + \mathbf{f}_s^B = \rho_s \ddot{\mathbf{d}}_s \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}_s$ is the arterial wall stress tensor, \mathbf{f}_s^B are the body forces per unit volume, ρ_s is the arterial wall density and $\ddot{\mathbf{d}}_s$ is the local acceleration of the solid.

The fluid and the solid domains are coupled through displacement compatibility and traction equilibrium as it is shown in the following equations:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_s \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_s = \boldsymbol{\tau}_f \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_f \quad (x, y, z) \in \Gamma_{FSI}^S \cap \Gamma_{FSI}^F, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{d}_s = \mathbf{d}_f \quad (x, y, z) \in \Gamma_{FSI}^S \cap \Gamma_{FSI}^F. \quad (9)$$

where Γ_{FSI}^S is a group of points on the arterial wall and Γ_{FSI}^F is a group of points on the lumen. Eq. (8) depicts that the solid and the fluid stresses that act on the common interface of the two domains (the group of points that belongs to both domains) are in equilibrium, whereas Eq. (9) shows that the common interface of the two domains exhibit the same displacements. A full cardiac cycle was used in all cases. The arterial wall was modeled as a hyperelastic 5-parameter Mooney-Rivlin material having the following coefficient values deriving from the stretch ratio to Cauchy stress diagrams that were created after a uniaxial extension study [11]: C10=9267 Pa, C01=3508 Pa, C20=3.0546E+05 Pa, C11=1.183E+06 Pa, C02=5.0451E+05 Pa and D1=1E-05. Moreover, the fibrotic plaque that was segmented in both models was treated as a Neo-Hookean model with an initial Shear modulus of 30 kPa and an incompressibility parameter of 1E-05, respectively [11].

The duration of each cycle was calculated based on the patient-specific pulse rate and was calculated as 60/pulse rate. Each cycle was divided into timesteps of 0.05 sec in order to achieve better accuracy and convergence. All simulations were carried out using ANSYS® v16.2. The element size was set to 0.16 mm or lower and constituted only of tetrahedra. The convergence criterion was set to 10⁻⁴ and the iteration limit was 150 for each timestep. Time-averaged ESS values, total area of low ESS (i.e., <2 Pa) and flow velocities were calculated for each model. Furthermore, geometrical parameters such as minimum lumen area (i.e., stenosis region), NASCET stenosis degree, maximum principal stress distribution, inlet, ICA and ECA area are also calculated for the comparison.

3 Results

The first analysis was based on geometrical findings mainly. We focused on the area of the inlet and the two outlets respectively. Table 1 depicts the calculated areas for the inlet and the outlets for each 3D lumen model, respectively. Moreover, the stenosis degree as calculated using the NASCET criterion, as well as the total wall volume and the plaque volume, respectively.

Table 1 Geometrical attributes of the two models

Case ID	CCA area	ICA area	ECA area	Wall volume	Plaque volume	Stenosis degree
049_US	41.7 mm ²	27.8 mm ²	15.5 mm ²	987 mm ³	180 mm ³	41.7%
049_MRI	46.6 mm ²	23.7 mm ²	22.1 mm ²	1034 mm ³	134 mm ³	39.4%

Following the geometrical analysis, we then performed a comparison in terms of crucial hemodynamic parameters such as peak TAESS and areas of low ESS, respectively. Table 2 contains the calculated values of the aforementioned parameters for all 3D models.

Table 2 Calculated biomechanical forces and hemodynamic parameters

Case ID	Peak ESS at stenosis	Area of low ESS (<2 Pa)/Total Vessel Area (%)	Maximum principal stress
049_US	56.2 Pa	16	4.57 kPa
049_MRI	46.3 Pa	13.2	3.76 kPa

Fig. 2 Areas of low WSS for the MRI-based model (left image) and the US-based model (right image). The ICAs in both cases present with large areas of low WSS

Fig. 3 WSS distribution for the MRI-based model (left image) and the US-based model (right image)

Fig. 4 Maximum principal stress distribution throughout the inner wall of the artery

4 Discussion

In this case study, we presented a comparison of the full 3D models (lumen, outer wall and plaques) that derived from two important carotid imaging modalities, US and MRI, using the images of the same patient. An initial geometrical comparison was done to examine how the two models correlate in terms of areas at the distal parts of the artery, volumes regarding the wall and the plaque components and stenosis degree, as calculated using the NASCET method and then, using the same patient-specific boundary conditions for each case, finite element-based two-way fluid structure interaction blood flow simulations were carried out to investigate the similarity of the calculated hemodynamic parameters

such as TAESS, areas of low ESS and maximum principal stress values, respectively. Starting with the geometrical features, the diameters of the vessels presented with moderately close values. However, due to the nature of US, the surface details of the final US-based 3D models were evidently lower compared to the MRI-based models, something expected, since US does not provide the amount of information that can be derived from the MRI sequences due to its two-dimensional nature. The calculated volumes were also pretty similar when dealing with the arterial wall (i.e., 4.5% difference), whereas when dealing with the plaque components, a much larger difference was observed (i.e. 24%). Furthermore, the US-based models were much smoother than the MRI-based ones, which resulted to a more linearized flow which in sequence, produced lower ESS values than the MRI-based models, hence explaining the larger low TAWSS areas. Another important finding is that the location of the areas of low ESS matched the two modalities quite accurately (Fig. 2), which is quite promising. As it can be seen from Fig. 2, both models exhibit areas of low TAWSS throughout almost the entire length of the ICA, capturing even the angle at which the phenomenon is observed. Moreover, the same applies to the areas that demonstrated peak TAWSS values for each case, leading to a reasonable qualitative match for the TAWSS distribution throughout the examined vessels. These findings are pretty promising, since US is a fully non-invasive imaging modality with minimal patient distress, especially when compared to the arduous MRI examination, which, if performed using an extended acquisition protocol (i.e., pre and post contrast sequences, with and without fat saturation enabled), can last almost 60-90 minutes. Furthermore, US entails minimal preparation, it is trivial for the clinician and the examination cost is apparently lower. Nevertheless, the limited dataset that was used in this study does not allow us to draw solid assumptions on whether US can be used to assess the hemodynamic status of the carotid vasculature. Additionally, to perform a comprehensive 3D reconstruction using only US images, an extended acquisition protocol must be followed that will include the common carotid and both the internal and external carotids for an adequate length in both longitudinal and transversal views. This is a critical parameter for an accurate 3D reconstruction from US images. Our next phase is to expand the dataset to produce more solid results. If the results of the extended comparison follow the trajectory of this work, then US-derived 3D models will be able to be used for either simple or more complex (i.e., FSI) flow analysis and provide crucial results to the risk stratification tool that is being developed in the context of the TAXINOMISIS study.

5 Conclusions

In this study we presented a comparison between US-based and MRI-based 3D carotid models in one representative case with a moderate stenosis (>50%) in the ICA. The produced results exhibited that US-derived 3D models can be used for a preliminary evaluation of the hemodynamic status of the carotid vasculature and can identify areas that are either prone to develop atherosclerotic plaque or areas that exhibit high ESS values and can initiate the destabilization of the already

existing plaque. Additional analysis must be made in a large dataset to determine the risk thresholds for the US models, so that they can be used in a broader level in everyday clinical practice.

5 Acknowledgement

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 755320, as part of the TAXINOMISIS project.

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